

MANAGEMENT OF THE USE OF DUAL EDUCATION IN IMPROVING THE SKILLS OF PERSONNEL WORKING IN THE TOURISM SECTOR IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *The role of qualified personnel in all sectors of the economy is high. The need for qualified workers and specialists in the production, industry and service sectors is very high. Especially now, in almost all areas of the tourism sector, achieving high efficiency without a qualified personnel factor is a difficult issue. Therefore, improving the skills of personnel working in the tourism sector remains as important as ever. In this regard, the use of foreign experience, which has been giving its positive results from year to year, can be an appropriate solution to the problem. Currently, many foreign countries are using the dual form of education in the training of qualified personnel. The dual form of education is a form in which the theoretical part of education is conducted in a higher educational institution, and the practical part is conducted in the workplace. This system is tripartite, that is, beneficial to the institute, the enterprise and the student, and serves to train modern and qualified specialists for the enterprises of the sector. This article examines the managing the training of highly qualified personnel based on a dual education format in the tourism sector.*

Keywords: *tourism industry, dual education, foreign experience, human resources management.*

Annotatsiya. *Iqtisodiyotning barcha sohalarida malakali kadrlarning o`rni yuqori hisoblanadi. Ishlab chiqarish, sanoat va xizmat ko`rsatish sohalarida malakali ishchi va mutaxassislariga bo`lgan ehtiyoj yuqori ko`rsatkichlarni tashkil etmoqda. Ayniqsa hozirgi kunda turizm sohasining deyarli barcha yo`nalishlarida yetuk kadrlar omilisiz yuqori samaraga erishish murakkab masaladir. Shunday ekan, turizm sohasida faoliyat yuritayotgan kadrlar malakasini oshirish har doimgidek muhim masala bo`lib qolmoqda. Ushbu masalada yildan yilga o`zining ijobiy samarasini berib kelayotgan xorij tajribalaridan foydalanish muammoning o`rinli yechimi bo`la oladi. Hozirgi kunda ko`plab xorij mamlakatlari malakali kadrlar tayyorlashda dual ta`lim shaklidan foydalanmoqda. Dual ta`lim shakli - ta`limning nazariy qismi oliy ta`lim muassasada, amaliy qismi esa ish joyida o`tkaziladigan shakli hisoblanib, ushbu tizim uch taraflama, ya`ni institut, korxonalar va talabaga manfaatli bo`lib, soha korxonalariga zamonaviy va malakali mutaxassislarni tayyorlashga xizmat qiladi. Bevosita ta`limning ushbu shakli turizm sohasini rivojlantirishda ham juda ahamiyatli hisoblanadi. Ushbu maqolada turizm sohasida dual ta`lim shakli asosida yuqori malakali kadrlar tayyorlashni boshqarish masalasi ko`rib chiqiladi.*

Kalit so`z: *turizm sohasi, dual ta`lim shakli, xorij tajribasi, kadrlar boshqaruvi.*

Аннотация. *Квалифицированные кадры играют важную роль во всех секторах экономики. Потребность в квалифицированных рабочих и специалистах в сфере производства, промышленности и услуг очень высока. Особенно сегодня достижение высокой эффективности практически во всех сферах туристической отрасли без квалифицированного кадрового фактора является сложной задачей. Поэтому повышение квалификации кадров, работающих в сфере туризма, остается актуальным как никогда.*

В этой связи использование зарубежного опыта, который из года в год дает положительные результаты, могло бы стать разумным решением проблемы. В настоящее время во многих зарубежных странах дуальное образование используется для подготовки квалифицированных кадров. Дуальная форма обучения — форма обучения, при которой теоретическая часть обучения осуществляется в высшем учебном заведении, а практическая — на рабочем месте. Такая система выгодна трем сторонам: институту, предприятию и студенту и служит подготовке современных и квалифицированных специалистов для предприятий отрасли. В статье рассматривается опыт зарубежных стран по организации подготовки высококвалифицированных кадров на основе дуального формата образования в сфере туризма.

***Ключевые слова:** индустрия туризма, дуальное образование, зарубежный опыт, управление человеческими ресурсами.*

MAIN BODY

Among the many areas being developed in our country, the work carried out by the state and representatives of the industry to improve the skills of personnel working in various areas of the tourism industry, including increasing the experience of highly qualified personnel working in all areas of the tourism industry, is bearing fruit year after year. These works have contributed to increasing interest in the tourism industry among young people, increasing the demand for this area in educational institutions, as well as increasing the number of people interested in tourism, and increasing the number and number of educated, talented, and enterprising highly qualified personnel who serve actively and honestly. As a result of the large-scale reforms being implemented by our state to develop the tourism industry, this area is increasingly developing. Mature, modern personnel are of decisive importance in further developing the industry and achieving the lofty goals set by the head of our state. For this reason, specific measures are being taken to train and improve the skills of personnel in the tourism sector, as well as to expand international cooperation in this regard. In particular, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures to develop the spheres of education and science in the new period of development of Uzbekistan” No. PF-6108 dated November 6, 2020, stipulated the introduction of a dual education system in vocational educational institutions in order to introduce practice-oriented educational programs starting from the 2021/2022 academic year. In addition, in recent years, a number of resolutions and decrees have been introduced to widely promote the dual education form in the education system, including in the tourism sector, to use the effective opportunities of this form of education.

Dual education, that is, a system combining practical and theoretical education, is very widespread in Germany, and many scientists have expressed their opinions on this issue;

Alfred D.W. (Alfred M. Schmidt) believes that the socio-economic importance of the dual education system is great, arguing that this system helps students gain experience in the workplace and acquire the necessary skills to enter the labor market.

Another German researcher, Ralph E. (Ralf T. Gunter), emphasizes that dual education is aimed at improving the quality of education and that through this system, students have the opportunity to combine theoretical knowledge with practical training.

German scientist Klaus H. (Klaus J. Kohn) considers dual education important in terms of strengthening cooperation between teachers and employers. He says that it increases the quality of

education through the active participation of teachers in the workplace, as well as through the opportunity to exchange practical experience.

According to scientist Birgit B. (Birgit B. Schneider), the dual education system plays an important role in ensuring economic stability and job opportunities for young people. In her opinion, through this system, students not only gain knowledge, but also develop social skills.

In the educational programs offered by higher education institutions engaged in training personnel for tourism, it is observed that the knowledge and skills provided to young students lag behind the requirements of the time, there is a shortage of qualified professors and teachers who are true representatives of the industry, and there is a lack of modern equipment in universities. In addition, the lack of proper integration between educational programs and tourism enterprises is also causing a mismatch between the qualifications of these graduates and the job requirements in the tourism sector. In solving these problems, the main solution can be to introduce the effective experiences of foreign countries into the development of the sector. In order to train qualified and modern personnel in the tourism sector, several countries, including Germany, Spain, Austria and the USA, are effectively using the prospects of Dual education in their education systems. Personnel studying in the tourism sector undoubtedly need to acquire both theoretical and practical knowledge at the same time. In this case, the dual form of education is the most appropriate solution. Below we will consider the potential of dual education in the development of the tourism industry:

➤ What is dual course about tourism?

The main focus of the dual education course in tourism is organizing travel. People skills are required, as you learn how to identify customer needs and translate them into tourism services. A distinctive feature of the system is the mix of disciplines and specialist knowledge: This means that you will not only gain knowledge of tourism itself, but also business knowledge. During your studies, you will also study foreign languages, geography, politics and gastronomy, so that you can later develop new offers for the tourism industry.

➤ What can you do after completing the dual education course in tourism?

The employment opportunities in the tourism sector are very wide, so you have a good chance of finding the right job for you. Possible areas of activity include marketing, the hotel industry or hotel management, as well as sports, health and wellness tourism and event management. You can find work in travel agencies, hotels or similar companies.

➤ What degree can you obtain with a dual education course in tourism?

A dual education course in tourism helps you to obtain your first professional qualification. With an integrated course of study, you will obtain a relevant qualification - for example, a tourism employee.

➤ Why is it important to choose a dual education course in tourism?

There is a wide range of jobs in the tourism industry and therefore many potential positions in different areas - so the work is very diverse. However, due to the popularity of the tourism sector among employees, competition is also quite high. Thus, a dual education course gives an advantage over applicants who can only demonstrate academic qualifications. A dual degree course in tourism also offers good opportunities for specialization and the opportunity to continue your education. Internationally oriented universities or vocational academies also offer the opportunity to complete a semester abroad.

As can be seen from the above information, the role of the dual education system in training personnel in the tourism sector is very high. The issue of using this experience in the development

of Uzbek tourism and improving the skills of personnel in it is currently being studied. In June of this year, at a videoconference meeting chaired by the Head of State Shavkat Mirziyoyev, a number of tasks were set to radically improve the professional education system and effectively implement dual education in practice based on the experience of Germany. In particular, in accordance with the resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 23, 2024, a number of procedures were established in our country to further improve the system of continuing education in the tourism sector in accordance with international standards, to establish a system of training highly qualified competitive personnel in accordance with the modern requirements of the labor market, to ensure the integration of science, education and production, and to bring the quality of services to a level that fully meets world standards. According to it, from the 2024/2025 academic year, a system of training personnel in the tourism and hotel industry in state higher educational institutions will be established on the basis of three-year higher education programs.

Also, in accordance with the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 16.01.2025 No. 14 “On measures to organize a dual education system in the higher education system”, starting from the 2025/2026 academic year, it was determined to gradually establish training in the higher education system based on dual education, including the establishment of the “Professional Owner” dual education system. The main goals and objectives of dual education were also outlined. According to it;

The purpose of dual education is to:

- strengthen the theoretical knowledge of students;
- formation of practical skills in students in the field of study (specialty) they are studying;
- organization of learning experiences related to production (as well as organizational and managerial) activities at enterprises, regardless of their organizational and legal form;
- development of students' professional and creative interests;
- ensuring that graduates have the necessary practical skills and qualifications to work with modern equipment and technologies;
- increasing the competitiveness of students through training in a higher educational institution and an enterprise, as well as introducing new teaching technologies into the educational process of a higher educational institution.

The main tasks of dual education are:

- training specialists in accordance with the needs of the labor market, sectors of the economy and development prospects;
- improving social partnership;
- ensuring the mobility of the content and structure of educational programs of a higher educational institution;
- create sufficient conditions for students to gain professional experience in production conditions;
- create opportunities for students to study and work.

All of this work is aimed at improving the skills of personnel working in the tourism sector and training specialists who meet world standards

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Analyzing the above data, we can conclude that the tourism industry is currently one of the fastest growing industries. Undoubtedly, the issue of personnel working in this industry is in the first place in the development of the industry. In particular, the tourism industry is an industry with

great potential for economic development and cultural exchange in Uzbekistan. In recent years, the decisions and work being taken by the head of our state to develop the industry, especially the development of a number of strategies for training personnel and improving the industry, using the experience of countries with developed tourism in the development of the industry, are helping to solve problems related to personnel. Also, the effective use of the achievements of this program in training personnel for the tourism market of Uzbekistan using the dual education programs mentioned above in the education system will soon bear fruit.

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